

An Information System Prototype for Analysis of Astronaut/Computer Interaction During Simulated EVA

Michael A. Mackin
 NASA Glenn Research Center
 21000 Brookpark Rd
 Cleveland, OH 44135
 216-433-5326
 Michael.A.Mackin@nasa.gov

Phillip T. Gonia
 NASA Glenn Research Center
 21000 Brookpark Rd
 Cleveland, OH 44135
 216-433-2176
 Philip.Gonia@nasa.gov

José A. Lombay-González
 NASA Glenn Research Center
 21000 Brookpark Rd
 Cleveland, OH 44135
 216-433-8479
 Jose.A.Lombay-Gonzalez@nasa.gov

Abstract— During human exploration of space, a suited crewmember needs effective and accurate information about their spacesuit's operation. Ideally, the information should be presented in a manner that provides real-time situational awareness and increases task efficiency and operational autonomy. Typically, however, the effective display of information has been limited by the relatively low resolution of radiation-tolerant sunlight readable displays and the low processing power available on currently deployed spacesuits. As part of NASA's Enabling Technology Development and Demonstrations Program, a prototype EVA Information System has been constructed to test and study human-computer interaction and system operations. In one tested configuration, the Information System provides acquisition and display of science data via a cuff-mounted graphical display and keypad and features a camera capable of capturing both still images and high-definition video. The Information System provides a capability for astronaut-computer interaction beyond currently deployed state-of-the-art EVA systems. Using the Information System, crewmembers may receive timeline-based procedures, general procedures, and text messages from either ground or space-based EVA mission controllers. Additionally, using the EVA Information System prototype, crewmembers can generate and analyze scientific artifacts (pictures, videos, or voice notes) and deliver them to the ground-based science team for detailed analysis. This paper discusses the software architecture of the prototype Information System software and the user feedback obtained from field testing the system at NASA's Desert Research and Technologies Studies (Desert RATS) activity.

support, thermal protection, and communication capabilities necessary for space station crewmembers to work in space.

The EMU suit includes a computerized Caution and Warning System (CWS) that monitors the operation of the suit systems. The primary means of human-computer interaction with the CWS is through the Display and Control Module (DCM) (Figure 1). The DCM contains a 12-character liquid crystal text display and several hand-operated toggle switches.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The current generation of the NASA spacesuit onboard the International Space Station is known as the Extravehicular Mobility Unit (EMU) [1]. The EMU provides the life

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Figure 1 - Display and Control Module (DCM)

For spacesuits, there are several key environmental factors, including intense sunlight and the need for bulky pressurized gloves, which drive the design of the human interfaces to computerized systems. For the DCM, these factors limit the minimum spacing allowed between control switches and constrain the DCM display to reflective liquid crystal technology [2].

The DCM provides the core computing capabilities required to manage and control the EMU suit's life support system. Astronauts are also provided cuff-mounted, text-based procedure cue cards for guidance in contingency situations.

For future EVA missions, an EVA Information System (EVAIS) processor would supplement the future suit's life-critical CWS system and replace the procedural cue cards. Since a future EVAIS would be suit-mounted, it must be

small, lightweight, and consume a minimum of electrical power. Additionally, since the EVAIS interacts with critical components of the suit avionics, it must operate robustly and in a fail-safe manner. Unlike the CWS, however, the EVAIS is not a life-critical system. A failure of the EVAIS reduces the effectiveness of an EVA crewmember, but is not considered mission critical.

NASA envisions future space missions to a Near Earth Object (NEO), such as an asteroid or Mars. An EVA Information System is necessary in order to replace some of the operational capabilities lost due to the relatively long communication delay between the EVA crewmembers and Earth. The functional goals of the EVAIS are to

- Increase crew autonomy
- Improve crew task efficiency
- Increase crew situational awareness

NASA and other researchers have previously developed EVA components meant to improve the computer interactions of suited astronauts. Some of these efforts involved flight hardware [3], while others were prototypes targeted at various field analog missions or independent trials. [4-7]

These systems also explored some new possibilities for astronaut-computer interaction, including the use of speech recognition and helmet-mounted displays. [8-13]

2. APPROACH

As part of NASA's spacesuit engineering team, NASA Glenn Research Center (GRC) is responsible for developing the next generation suits' Power, Avionics, and Software (PAS) subsystem. In order to test operational concepts for the EVAIS and to develop capabilities for future missions, NASA is testing prototype equipment at the Desert Research and Technologies Studies (Desert RATS) field outings in the desert north of Flagstaff, Arizona.

Desert RATS offers a NASA-led team of engineers, crewmembers, and scientists from across the country an opportunity to collaborate and conduct technology development research. The terrain conditions offer a good stand-in for future exploration mission destinations.

At Desert RATS, the correct type and amount of information needed by an EVA crewmember can be evaluated. Since suit electronics must be small, lightweight, and use minimal electrical power, the suit cannot afford to have any unnecessary "bells and whistles." The EVA PAS team at GRC spent over a year working with crewmembers and other stakeholders to better understand their needs and expectations for this system. The stakeholders made it clear that the crew must not be hindered with too much information, since that would impede, rather than help, operations.

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In addition, since the EVAIS technology development effort is flight driven, fielded prototypes must have a realistic upgrade path to radiation tolerant flight hardware.

The EVAIS development team supported both the 2010 and 2011 Desert RATS excursions, with the results of the 2010 trials used to improve the 2011 implementation.

For the 2010 and 2011 excursions, the EVAIS team focused on infusing new technology into previously identified EVAIS concepts. Since EVA technology development efforts for embedded-computer-based helmet-mounted displays and speech recognition systems were not yet ready for field testing, these efforts were deferred to future outings.

3. EVAIS PROTOTYPE

The prototype EVAIS consists of an embedded computer, a cuff-mounted flat panel display, and a high definition (HD) video camera. The system also includes an electronic compass and a Global Positioning System (GPS) receiver as a stand-in for the eventual flight navigation system. The embedded computer and navigational equipment (the GPS receiver and electronic compass) are contained within an avionics box that is mounted on the crew backpack. The HD camera is also mounted to the backpack. The cuff display is worn on either the right or left forearm of the test subject. The EVAIS is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2 - EVA Information System (EVAIS)

During actual EVAs, a crewmember wearing a pressure garment must interact with and control the EVAIS. However, for the Desert RATS testing in 2010 and 2011, a shirt-sleeve backpack was worn in order to reduce the logistical and cost overhead associated with testing while wearing a pressurized suit. Audio and data communication on the Desert RATS shirt-sleeve suit was provided by the NASA Kennedy Space Center.

Cuff Display Assembly

Since conventional terrestrial computer-input devices such as a mouse or touch pad are difficult to use with a

pressurized glove, they were not considered as viable computer input devices for the Desert RATS EVAIS. Instead, crewmembers interact with the EVAIS using the cuff display assembly.

The cuff display assembly contains a 3 in. x 4 in. sunlight-readable flat panel display. Around the periphery of the display are eight pushbuttons: one dedicated single-function button and seven programmable function buttons. The dedicated single-function button is allocated to the most common task of EVA crewmembers: recording crew field notes (CFNs).

Crew Field Notes

For geologists, much of the data that they gather when working out in the field is their verbal observations dictated into a recorder. Using the dedicated CFN button on the cuff display, a crewmember geologist activates the camera and built-in digital video recorder (DVR), gathers a rock sample, holds it up in front of the camera, and provides a verbal description by speaking into a headset microphone. In a similar fashion, the crewmember can capture still image snapshots of rock samples. The GPS receiver, contained within the backpack avionic box, provides a location stamp for all CFNs and still images. When these items are recorded, the GPS location place-marks are transmitted to a surface rover over a wireless communication network. The CFNs are stored on the EVAIS, and at the end of the day, the processed data is transferred to the rover to match up with the place-marks sent during the EVAs. The data is ultimately transmitted to the Mission Control Center for analysis.

4. EVAIS SOFTWARE ARCHITECTURE

The following sections describe the EVAIS software architecture and provide details about the EVAIS Human Machine Interface (HMI) components.

The EVAIS HMI is written in ActionScript 2.0 and executes within the Flash Lite 3.1 environment. Flash Lite is a lightweight version of the Adobe Flash player, intended for use on mobile devices, such as cell phones or other embedded platforms. An advantage of using the ActionScript programming language is the ease with which the application may be ported to other web-based platforms. In fact, prior to Desert RATS testing, the EVAIS HMI was transferred to a remotely accessible server allowing pre-trial evaluation and test subject training of the system. The EVAIS HMI is hosted on an embedded real-time operating system.

Since a Flash application, for security reasons, is prohibited from directly accessing local hardware devices, the EVAIS software uses a *web services architecture*. The Flash HMI communicates with a number of separate software server processes that directly control the EVAIS hardware components (i.e. camera, GPS receiver, and electronic compass.) The HMI and web services processes exchange

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data through eXtensible Markup Language (XML)-formatted data exchanges.

EVAIS Application

The main EVAIS application starts automatically when the EVAIS is powered up. In order to enhance sunlight readability, contrasting font colors and backgrounds are used. An effort has been made to keep the screen as simple and streamlined as possible.

The display contains two status banners across the top of the display and two soft-key menus along the right and bottom of the HMI display (Figure 3). The soft-key menu legends correspond with the locations of the seven programmable cuff pushbuttons. The top banner displays two crewmember-controlled clocks: mission time (EV PET) and stopwatch time (TIME LF) as well as the local time (LOCAL or GMT). The second banner (right below the top banner) displays altitude (ALTITUDE) in meters above sea level and magnetic compass heading (HEADING) in degrees. In the 2010 version of the EVAIS, these banners were not present. They were added in 2011 at the request of the crew, so that they would have most of the most commonly used status indicators available at a glance.

Abbreviated legends on the soft key menus were necessary in order to allow large font sizes while still limiting the amount of screen real estate that was used. Smaller fonts were more difficult to see in bright sunlight.

Camera Viewfinder

The default EVAIS HMI screen is the camera viewfinder screen (Figure 3.) The camera viewfinder provides a real-time view of the HD video camera image. It is the most commonly used EVAIS display. The ability to view video, in real-time, is a key new capability demonstrated to EVA crewmembers in 2011. The EVAIS displays video at a resolution of 480 x 272 and updates at a rate of 24 frames per second.

Figure 3 - EVAIS HMI

The video camera status indicator is shown in the bottom right-hand corner of the display screen. Nominally, a red record (REC) indicator is shown indicating that the EVA

camera is operating correctly. In Figure 3, the red FIELD NOTE indicator is also illuminated, showing that the crewmember is actively recording a video geological field note.

Still Image Capture

Crewmembers are able to capture still images from the HD camera using the PICT key. When the PICT key is pressed, the EVAIS begins a three second countdown before the image is captured. The countdown time is displayed as a large yellow digit centered within the image viewfinder, as shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4 - Image Capture Countdown

After an image is captured, the crew reviews the image and uses a soft-key to either reject the image, in which case the digital file is deleted, or assigns one of three possible image download priorities. For rejected images, the crew can easily reframe, recompose, and recapture the desired scientific image.

Maps

The map application, as shown in Figure 5, provides basic positional awareness to the crew and is activated by the MAP menu key. The map application supports scrolling the map both vertically and horizontally, as well as zooming in and out. Also provided is a SETTINGS menu that gives the crew member access to options for resetting the map position, so that the location marker is centered on the map display, or resetting map zoom level to the system-defined default.

The EVAIS HMI displays the geographical location of the crewmember using information obtained from the backpack-mounted GPS receiver. To increase visibility, the location marker consists of a suited crewmember icon overlaid on the center of a pulsating circle. The location of the icon is updated every 10 seconds. The pulsating circle provides an easy-to-spot position beacon for quickly determining the status of the GPS receiver and locating the current geographical location of the user on the displayed map.

During field testing, it is possible for an EVA crewmember to lose GPS position signals if the crewmember is located behind a rock or other large geological feature. In order to quickly communicate the crewmember's GPS status, a simple color scheme has been devised. In this scheme, the color of the position beacon is one of the following:

Green: The GPS position beacon pulsates from green to blue indicating that the GPS data is being received and is valid.

Amber: The GPS position beacon pulsates from amber/yellow to blue, indicating that the GPS status is changing.

Red: The GPS position beacon pulsates from red to blue indicating that the GPS data has been invalid for more than 20 seconds. The crew marker and map are not updated while in this state.

In addition to the location of EVA assets (i.e. other crewmembers and the rover), the map shows a small flag icon to indicate the location of crew field notes and can also, when enabled, display a *bread crumb* trail which indicates the historical traverse path that a crewmember has followed.

To prevent screen clutter, crewmembers may deactivate various categories of map markers. Crew markers, rover markers, waypoint markers, or breadcrumb markers may all be selectively deactivated.

Figure 5 - Map View

Timelines and Procedures

As missions start being performed farther away from the Earth, communication between crewmembers and ground support changes from a continuous stream to more intermittent bursts, requiring that crewmembers operate more autonomously. The procedure viewer is a software application that aims to improve the autonomy of EVA crewmembers by providing electronically displayed task procedures so that they can operate efficiently without the guidance of Mission Control.

The timeline application provides the crewmember with access to EVA-specific procedures arranged along a timeline. Since EVA crews operate in pairs, the timeline

allows each paired crewmember access to their partner's procedures. The procedures are organized along a vertically oriented timeline. The timeline may have customizable increments, but by default, the tasks are in increments of 15 minutes. A selected procedure is highlighted so that it stands out within the list, as shown in Figure 6. The timeline, along the left vertical axis in this example, provides for an interval between tasks of 15 minutes. For a timeline beginning at time indication of 0000, an elapsed time of one hour is indicated with the notation of 0100, two hours with 0200, and so on.

Figure 6 - EVAIS Timeline

The edge-keys, arranged along the bottom and right edges of the cuff display, are used to navigate through the list of procedures. Once the desired procedure is highlighted, the SELECT button is pressed and it loads the procedure into the procedure viewer application.

EVAIS Procedures

EVAIS procedures are XML-based text files meant to be composed of concise instructions that guide a crewmember through planned EVA tasks (Figure 7).

Figure 7 - EVAIS Procedure Viewer

The procedures may contain both images and text. The procedure viewer is the EVAIS application that displays procedures and provides the crewmember with a means of navigating through them. When the crewmember is finished with a procedure (has reached the last page of the procedure), the procedure displays the DONE menu item at

the bottom right corner of the screen, as shown in Figure 7. Selection of the DONE menu closes the procedure viewer and reopens the timeline application that displays a checkmark next to the completed procedure's name.

EVAIS Drawings

Crewmembers may access EVA supplemental information using the EVAIS drawings component. This EVAIS component provides user access to schematic drawings, maps, or other images. The EVAIS provides a zoomable interface so that the crewmember can pan, scroll, and zoom through informational images or drawings. Providing a variety of zoom levels allows the crewmember to view the overall context of an image or drawing at low resolution or to zoom-in to see a detailed, high resolution view.

Figure 8 shows an example of an image with the route plan and waypoints for a Desert RATS EVA traverse. Using the EVAIS drawings component, crewmembers may zoom to particular locations (using the ZIN or the ZOUT soft-keys) or access a sub-menu providing scroll capability.

Figure 8 - EVAIS Drawing Example

Text Messaging

For NEO missions, long communication delays make audio communication with Earth difficult. As a communication aid, one-way text messaging is provided by the EVAIS. Text messages provide a way to deliver a record of contingency plans or special instructions to the crew. When a new text message is delivered to a crewmember, a blinking yellow TEXT message legend appears on the cuff display status banner. Crewmembers access the contents of the text message by pressing the TXT MSG soft-key.

5. RESULTS

Overall, the prototype EVAIS performed as expected during the Desert RATS field-testing. The system withstood the rigorous desert environment and proved to be a valuable operational tool to the crew and to the science-support team. Since this was a first-generation prototype, there were known design characteristics that will need improvement for an eventual flight system. The testing provided an opportunity for thorough evaluation of the system, which

not only confirmed suspected deficiencies, but also revealed new areas for improvement. In addition, responses and feedback from the crew, mission operations, and mission scientists provided useful insight on areas for future improvement and capabilities. Comments and observation of usage patterns and behaviors during on-line and in-person training sessions, as well as from in-the-field testing, provided valuable insights to relevant astronaut-computer interactions.

Improvements to the EVAIS were made for Desert RATS field testing in 2011, based upon observations, comments, and suggestion provided at the 2010 field trials. A dedicated EVAIS concept-development session was also held with geologists, crewmember representatives, operations managers, and scientists between the 2010 and 2011 field trials in order to solicit opinions and recommendations for system upgrades.

After the 2010 trials, the majority of the recommendations for improvement that were received from the crew were related to the HD camera. Because previous stakeholder interviews had put a low priority on real-time video, the crew did not have video capability during the 2010 trials. Crewmembers probably underestimated their video needs due to previous flight experience in which the EMU video was viewed in real-time by Intra-Vehicular Activity (IVA) astronauts or ground personnel who then choreographed the crewmembers' activities. Without video feedback, it was difficult to properly point the suit cameras. Periodically, context shots and detailed sample shots were cut off and out of focus. The crew unanimously recommended that the camera field-of-view be displayed real-time on the cuff display. Also, in 2011, in addition to new video display capabilities, still image snapshots were shown on the display immediately after acquisition, allowing the crew to see and evaluate the image quality and framing.

Camera operation was another matter of concern to the crewmembers. Image capture using the EVAIS is a fairly complex task. Crewmembers must press the EVAIS PICT soft-key and then compose an image containing a rock, soil sample, or geological item of interest, along with a numbered sample bag, within the camera viewfinder before the EVAIS image capture timer expires. However, crewmembers have a large reservoir of expertise and are highly motivated, so they quite quickly optimized the steps necessary to accomplish image capture. Crewmembers recognize the value, and expense, of every minute of EVA time. Several commented that the 5-second image capture count for still image acquisition used in 2010 was too long. One went to the trouble to calculate an estimate of the cost difference between operating with a 5-second or a 3-second image capture delay for a complete EVA lunar mission. Based on their recommendations, the image acquisition timer count was reduced to from 5 seconds to 3 seconds for 2011 and was changed from counting up (i.e. 1-2-3-4-5) prior to image capture to counting down (i.e. 3-2-1).

Since the EVA crewmembers were interested in maintaining their schedule of exploration, the mission timers and clocks that had been on a sub-menu in 2010 were moved to the status banners that display on most EVAIS screens. The banners allow the crewmembers to see, at a glance, the current time (in GMT), and the length of the current EVA in hours, minutes, and seconds. The banners also show the value of a user-configurable countdown clock.

The banner also includes altitude and heading indicators that were added primarily due to comments from the trained geologist crewmembers. They desired this functionality in order to refer more accurately to specific features in their recorded CFNs. One crewmember recommended that compass heading and altitude readings could be used by the crew to determine thickness of rock formations. To accommodate the request for accurate heading readings, an electronic compass was added to the EVAIS in 2011. The compass provides more accurate heading information than the GPS when a crewmember is stationary.

Another software application that received a significant amount of crew feedback was the map display. The crew commented that the way maps were implemented in 2010 was not very useful and should not have been used as a default display. As a first generation prototype, the team intentionally kept the maps application simple. The system showed only the crewmember's position on the map. The crew commented that it would have been more useful to track the location of the rover and the other EVA crewmembers on the map. Also, if the map showed a historical trail of the crewmember's EVA excursion, displayed science waypoints, and allowed the crewmember to see points on the map where they recorded CFNs, the maps application could become a useful tool for the crew to perform geologic mapping.

The crew also provided feedback on the display indicators associated with recording CFNs. They commented that icons used on the display were too subtle, so that it was not obvious when a note starts, stops, or when a still image capture is occurring. The icons were replaced in 2011 with colored legends such as the FIELD NOTE REC indicator.

The crew also commented that audible feedback (such as beeps or clicks through the headset) would be helpful to reinforce what is being shown the cuff display. For technical reasons, audio feedback was not implemented in 2011.

The crew was asked to provide feedback regarding whether the cuff screen size was adequate for crew procedures. They responded that the small screen area was not a hindrance for displaying procedures. However, they suggested that cuff procedures should be short and concise. The crew commented that these procedures should be comparable to aviation cockpit cue cards. In other words, the steps should have minimal text, i.e., just enough to be a memory jogger. It was also noted that the Apollo EVA cuff

checklists used a more abbreviated format than what is used today for Space Shuttle and International Space Station.

Upgrades to the EVAIS cuff display and housing were made in 2011. The cuff housing was made smaller and lower-profile, the view screen was made larger, and an additional pushbutton key was added. The design of the cuff was modified so that it was wearable on either the left or right arm, which was not the case in 2010.

6. FUTURE WORK

The EVAIS development team plans to transfer maturing technologies to the existing EVAIS prototype prior to flight hardware development. Future technologies for inclusion include helmet-mounted displays and speech recognition systems. Exploration crewmembers, especially those dealing with long communication delays, would also benefit from an automatic delivery of integrated packages of recorded audio, video, or textual instructions from ground-based controllers.

Additionally, the inclusion of an EVAIS telemetry system would provide a means to accurately obtain statistics about feature usage patterns and behaviors.

7. CONCLUSIONS

An evolvable EVAIS prototype suitable for analysis of astronaut-computer interactions during NASA Desert RATS field testing has been presented.

The primary user interface components described include a real-time video viewfinder, a Crew Field Note data recorder that creates a log of the scientific observations from the EVA. The field notes are time-stamped, location-stamped, and synchronized with recorded motion imagery and still imagery from the suit-mounted camera. Also described are a map display system, a timeline and procedure viewer, and a text messaging system.

A description of user interface changes due to observation and analysis of crew-computer interaction and user feedback has also been reported.

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9. BIOGRAPHIES

Michael A. Mackin is a member of the National Aeronautics and Space Administration Glenn Research Center Extravehicular Power Avionics and Software (PAS) team where he is lead engineer for the EVA Information System. Michael has a B.S. and M.S. in Electrical Engineering from the

University of Toledo. He is a member of NASA Glenn's Flight Software Engineering Branch and has previously worked on a variety of avionics and software research and development projects including the International Space Station power system, flywheel energy storage avionics and controls and, in collaboration with MetroHealth Medical Center in Cleveland, OH, an ambulatory heart arrhythmia detection system.

Philip T. Gonias is a software engineer with over 30 years of experience in the aerospace industry, 25 years of which include software engineering and currently supports the Flight Software Branch for NASA at the Glenn Research Center, Cleveland OH. He currently is the lead software engineer for the Advanced Exploration Systems (AES) Spacecraft Fire Safety Project.

José A. Lombay-González is a computer engineer currently supporting the Flight Software Engineering Branch at the National Aeronautics and Space Administration Glenn Research Center. As a junior computer engineer he supports the Power Avionics and Software team developing the technology for future spacesuits. José has a B.S. in Computer Engineering from the University of Puerto Rico, Mayagüez Campus (2009).